

Excursion in Nature

I. Scenario Description

There are three distributed collaborating users. One is a guide who is in a natural environment and walks through it so that it can be virtually and remotely visited by two other users (potentially people with disabilities), whom we will refer to as spectators. The guide wears smart glasses, an electronic nose, and two vibrating bracelets, one on each arm. The glasses, in addition to displaying information, have computing capabilities and are connected via Bluetooth to the rest of the devices. Each of the spectators is located at home and has a PC with a scent generator and a camera installed, along with the corresponding groupware, which incorporates facial expression and emotion recognition, what explains the presence of the camera focusing on the user.

R1: Spectators can lead the guide to the left or right during their nature excursion by pressing the corresponding button on the user interface. The guide follows their directions as follows: when both users point in the same direction, the system activates the vibrating bracelet on the corresponding arm, and the guide follows that direction (left or right). In case of a mismatch, the guide chooses the direction he/she prefers, but each spectator's choice will be displayed on the glasses.

R2: The facial expressions of the spectators, computed by their systems, are sent to the guide, who observes them through his glasses, thereby gaining insight into the spectators' experience.

R3: During the exploration, the guide's system distributes the scent of the natural environment, captured with the electronic nose, to the spectators, which is reproduced by their scent generators. ...

II. Awareness Description Diagrams

R2

R2: Durante la exploración, la expresión facial de los espectadores, computada en sus sistemas, es remitida al guía, que la observa en sus gafas, teniendo así una impresión de la experiencia de los espectadores.

R3

R3: During the exploration, the guide's system distributes the scent of the natural environment, captured with the electronic nose, to the spectators, which is reproduced by their scent generators.

References

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